

Effect of plant derivatives on brown planthopper (BPH) and whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) nymph emergence on rice

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We tested nine plant derivatives for their inhibitory effect on BPH and WBPH nymphs. Forty-day-old potted IR20 plants were sprayed with 1% oils of neem *Azadirachta indica* A. Juss, pinnai *Calophyllum inophyllum* L.,

pungam *Pungamia glabra* L., and illupai *Madhuca longifolia* Macbr var. *latifolia* Boxb. cheval; 2% seed extracts of neem, pinnai, pungam, and illupai; and 5% neem cake extract, using a baby hand sprayer. Treated plants were confined separately with five gravid females of BPH and of WBPH in three replications. Nymphal emergence was assessed daily for 1 wk after spraying.

All plant derivatives were effective in reducing emergence of planthoppers (see table). Highest BPH reduction was with 5% neem cake extract, followed by 2% pungam seed extract. Highest WBPH reduction was with 5% neem cake extract, followed by 2% neem seed kernel. □

Effect of plant derivatives on BPH and WBPH nymph emergence on rice.^a TNAU, Madurai, India.

Treatment	BPH		WBPH	
	Nymph emergence (no.)	Decrease from control (%)	Nymph emergence (no.)	Decrease from control (%)
1% neem oil	96 c (8.26)	31.7	93 e (9.60)	12
1% pinnai oil	118 d (10.23)	15.4	118 f (10.86)	0.6
1% pungam oil	89 c (9.42)	22.2	68 d (8.20)	25
1% illupai oil	107 cd (9.65)	20.2	96 e (9.76)	11
2% neem seed kernel	64 b (7.99)	34	43 b (6.59)	40
2% pinnai seed extract	97 cd (9.68)	20	108 f (10.4)	5
2% pungam seed extract	30 a (5.47)	55	53 c (7.26)	34
2% illupai seed extract	83 c (9.11)	25	74 d (8.60)	21
5% neem cake extract	24 a (4.86)	60	30 a (5.46)	50
	147 e (12.1)		120 g (10.93)	
LSD (P = 0.05)	1		1	

^aMean of 3 replications. Figures in parentheses are transformed values. In a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Using rice straw bundles to conserve beneficial arthropod communities in ricefields

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Population densities of spiders and other beneficial arthropods decreased greatly after rice harvest because of disruption of their habitats. Harvesting, irrigation, plowing, and harrowing activities leave vegetation only along bunds and field edges for refuge of these natural enemies of rice

pests. Conservation of these beneficial forms during crop-free periods is important to ensure adequate numbers to recolonize fields when the rice crop is established.

We evaluated using bundles of rice straw as habitats for arthropod predator and prey communities during crop-free periods in irrigated rice.

The bundles were prepared by arranging rice straw into cone-shaped tents about 30 cm in diameter at the bottom. One tent was placed in the center of each of 24 plots in a newly harvested field. Plots were 10 × 7 m. Arthropods were collected using a vacuum sampler (D-vac) 5 and 10 d after placing tents in the field. Samples were placed in vials containing 70% alcohol solution and brought to the laboratory for sorting and counting.

Significantly more arthropods were collected 10 d after placing the tents in the field (Fig. 1). Natural enemies collected included coleopterans--*Stilbus* spp., *Micraspis*, *Ophionea*; orthopterans--*Metioche*, *Anaxipha*; hymenopterans--*Telenomus* spp., ants, *Anagrus*, *Oligosita*, *Goniozus*, *Mymarid*, *Bracon*, and *Elasmus*. Spiders were the most abundant group. The most common spider species were *Callitrichia formosana* and *Lycosa pseudoannulata* (Fig. 2). There were

1. Arthropods collected from rice straw bundles placed in ricefields after harvest. IIRRI, 1989.

2. Spiders collected from rice straw bundles placed in ricefields after harvest. IRRI, 1989.

also *Oxyopes* spp., *Tetragnatha* spp., *Argiope* sp., and *Dyschiriognatha* sp.

Plants and leafhoppers also were collected. It is important that several species of pests colonize the tents because they are needed as food for the beneficial species. □

M-phase in eggs of *Nephotettix virescens* (Distant)

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Growth and development of *N. virescens* from fertilized egg (zygote) to maturity depend largely on a coordinated sequence of increases in cell numbers, size, and differentiation. Somatic egg cells undergo cyclic events, such as interphase and M-phase (mitotic). The M-phase is a critical stage in embryonic development and an ideal stage for preventing rice pest development. It includes nuclear (karyokinesis) and cytoplasmic (cytokinesis) divisions. We characterized the M-phase in *N. virescens* eggs.

The insect was mass-reared on TN1 rice plants in the IRRI insectary. Eggs were collected daily from 1 to 8 d after oviposition and the onset of cleavage or nuclear division determined. (At $30 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$, *N.*

virescens eggs normally hatch 9 d after oviposition.)

Eggs were placed on a spot-plate with 2-3 drops of Ringer's solution and squashed with a glass rod for 1 min. Extracted chorions were fixed with Carnoy's solution (3 parts ethyl alcohol, 1 part glacial acetic acid) for 20 min.

One drop was placed on a fresh glass slide and air-dried for 15 min. A drop of 60% acetic acid was added to each slide and allowed to stand another 10-20 min. One drop of lacto-aceto-orcein was added and the mixture squashed with a bent needle.

1. Frequency of M-phase during nuclear division in *N. virescens* eggs at different days after oviposition, IRRI, 1989. n = 1,900 eggs.

Slides were viewed under oil immersion objective (1250x) of a binocular microscope fitted with a linear micrometer.

The M-phase of cleavage was monitored in 1,900 eggs. No nuclear division was found the first 4 d, when embryogenic cells were at the prophase stage. Onset of the M-phase was on day 5; it increased on day 6. Frequency of nuclear division peaked on day 7-8. A range of 13-37 dividing nuclei was observed during peak periods. It appears 6- to 8-d-old eggs (eyespot stage to dark egg stage) are ideal for observing nuclear division stages (Fig. 1, 2). □

2. Egg cells of *N. virescens* undergoing different stages of mitosis. a = interphase, b = prophase, c = prometaphase, d = metaphase. IRRI, 1989.

Weed management

Yield loss to weeds in upland rice at Parwanipur, Nepal

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We assessed yield loss due to weeds in dry seeded upland rice at Parwanipur in 1988.

Ghaiya 2 (MW10) was seeded 18 Jun at 20-cm spacing. The experimental field was fertilized with 60-30-30 kg NPK/ha. Half the N and all the P and K were applied basal; the remaining N was topdressed in two equal splits at 25 and 55 d after seeding.

Ten 5- × 3-m plots with different levels of weed infestation were established. Two samples of weeds within a 1-m² quadrat placed randomly in each plot were taken before maturity.

Weeds were identified, dried, and weighed. Rice yield from 5.6-m² areas was converted into g/m². A simple linear regression and correlation analysis was used to assess rice yield loss due to weed infestation.

Echinochloa colona, *E. crus-galli*, *Cyperus difformis*, *C. iria*, and *C. rotundus* were dominant.

The linear relationship ($r = 0.9602^{**}$) between dry weed weight and rice yield was negative and highly significant (see figure). The regression analysis $Y = 294.579 - 1.0568^{**} (\pm 0.3638) X$ estimated the reduction in